

Refractometric Studies on the Interaction of Some Metal Acetylacetonates with Iodine

R. SAHAI*, V. SINGH and (Miss) REKHA VERMA

Department of Chemistry, V. S. S. D. College, Kanpur-208 002

Manuscript received 6 September 1979, accepted 30 December 1979

Formation of molecular complexes between metal acetylacetonates of Be(II), VO(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III) and Co(III) as donors and iodine as acceptor has been studied in carbon tetrachloride using refractometric and differential refractometric techniques. The equilibrium constants (K_1) and extent of electronic polarization (α) of these complexes have been determined. The refractometric titration technique has indicated 1:1 stoichiometry of these complexes. These data provide further support on the pseudo-aromatic character of metal acetylacetonate chelate rings.

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC¹, conductometric² and dielectric studies³ have indicated that like aromatics, co-ordinatively saturated, neutral monomeric metal acetylacetonates, $M(\text{acac})_n$, form molecular complexes with iodine by donation of electron density from chelate rings. In order to provide further support on the pseudo-aromatic character of metal acetylacetonate chelate rings, the charge-transfer complex formation ability of Be(II), VO(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III) and Co(III) chelate rings with iodine has been studied employing refractometric and differential refractometric techniques.

Experimental

Metal acetylacetonates of Be(II)⁴, VO(II)⁵, Al(III)⁶, Cr(III)⁷, Fe(III)⁸ and Co(III)⁹ were prepared and purified as reported in the literature. The acetylacetonone (BDH) was redistilled before use. Iodine (A.R.) was resublimed. Analytical grade carbon tetrachloride was redistilled before use.

Stock solutions of donors [$M(\text{acac})_n$ where $M = \text{Be(II), VO(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III) and Co(III)}$] and acceptor (iodine) were prepared by weighing on an analytical balance and then diluted to the desired volume in volumetric flasks by carbon tetrachloride. The solution employed for measurements were prepared from stock solutions by pipetting the calculated volumes into 10 ml volumetric flasks and then diluted subsequently with the same solvent. All the stock solutions were prepared on the day of measurements. All the measurements were carried out at room temperature.

The refractive indices have been measured by Bousch & Lomb refractometer, with an accuracy of ± 0.0002 . The equilibrium constant (K_1) and extent of electronic polarization (α) of 1:1 molecular complexes have been calculated by using equations (1, 2 and 3)

developed by Sahai *et al.*¹⁰⁻¹²,

$$\frac{\delta\phi}{C_D^0} = \frac{K_1 C_A^0}{\alpha(1 + K_1 C_A^0)} - \frac{K_1 \delta\phi}{(1 + K_1 C_A^0)^2} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\frac{\Delta\phi}{C_D^0} = \frac{K_1 C_A^0}{\alpha(1 + K_1 C_A^0)} - \frac{K_1 \Delta\phi}{(1 + K_1 C_A^0)^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\frac{\Delta\Omega C_{DA}}{C_D^0} = \frac{K_1 C_A^0}{\alpha(1 + K_1 C_A^0)} - \frac{K_1 \Delta\Omega C_{DA}}{(1 + K_1 C_A^0)^2} \quad \dots (3)$$

where C_D^0 and C_A^0 are the initial concentrations of donor (D) and acceptor(A) respectively, and α is the extent of electronic polarization. $\delta\phi$, $\Delta\phi$ and $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$ may be calculated by the following relations,

$$\delta\phi = 10^3(\phi - \phi_0) = 6000(n - n_0)n_0/(n_0^2 + 2)^2 \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\Delta\phi = 10^3(\phi - \phi_A) = 6000(n - n_A)n_A/(n_A^2 + 2)^2 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\Omega C_{DA} &= 10^3(\phi - \phi_D) - 10^3(\phi_A - \phi_0) \\ &= \{6000(n - n_D)n_D/(n_D^2 + 2)^2\} \\ &\quad - \{6000(n_A - n_0)n_0/(n_0^2 + 2)^2\} \quad \dots (6) \end{aligned}$$

where n , n_D , n_A , n_0 are the refractive indices of solution (donor + acceptor), donor, acceptor and solvent respectively. ϕ , ϕ_D , ϕ_A and ϕ_0 are the refraction per cm^2 due to solution, donor, acceptor and solvent respectively, which may be calculated as reported earlier^{10,11}. As expected from equations (1,2 and 3), the plots of $\delta\phi$ vs $\delta\phi/C_D^0$, $\Delta\phi$ vs $\Delta\phi/C_D^0$ and $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$ vs $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}/C_D^0$ were linear (Figs. 1, 2 and 3) with a slope $-K_1/(1 + K_1 C_A^0)^2$ and intercept $K_1 C_A^0/\alpha(1 + K_1 C_A^0)^2$. The values of K_1 and α given in Table 1 were calculated by the method of least-squares.

*To whom all correspondence should be addressed.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\delta\phi$ vs $\delta\phi / C_D^0$ for molecular complexes of metal acetylacetonates with iodine in carbon tetrachloride.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\Delta\phi$ vs $\Delta\phi / C_D^0$ for molecular complexes of metal acetylacetonates with iodine in carbon tetrachloride.

Results and Discussion

In order to calculate the equilibrium constants (K_1) through equations (1, 2 and 3), the refractive indices of solvent, acceptor, donor and solution (donor + acceptor) were first observed. The refraction per cm^3 of solvent (ϕ_0), acceptor (ϕ_A), donor (ϕ_D) and solution (ϕ) were then calculated as reported earlier^{10,11}. The difference in refraction per cm^3 of solution and solvent ($\delta\phi$), solution and acceptor ($\Delta\phi$), and the refraction per cm^3 due to charge-transfer complex ($\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$) have been calculated

Fig. 3. Plots of $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$ vs $\Delta\Omega C_{DA} / C_D^0$ for molecular complexes of metal acetylacetonates with iodine in carbon tetrachloride.

by equations (4, 6). An appreciable increase in $\delta\phi$ and $\Delta\phi$ was noticed with the increase of donor concentration and keeping the acceptor concentration constant. At this stage one may doubt, that the relative increase in $\delta\phi$ and $\Delta\phi$ may be due to the increase in donor concentration and not due to charge-transfer interaction. This problem has been solved by taking the refractive indices of donor and acceptor separately (as C_A^0 is constant throughout the experiment) and calculating ϕ_A and ϕ_D . On mixing 1 ml ($10^{-1} - 10^{-3} M$) of donor and 1 ml ($10^{-2} - 10^{-4} M$) of acceptor, the refractive indices (n) of the solution or ϕ , the refraction per cm^3 of solution increases appreciably with respect to that of separate component. This relative increase in ϕ has been interpreted due to charge-transfer interaction between the donors and acceptor, and it is not due to increase in donor concentration. This appreciable increase in $\delta\phi$ or $\Delta\phi$ may be interpreted due to the charge-transfer from the π -orbital of benzenoid ring of metal acetylacetonates to the σ^* -orbital of iodine¹.

The equilibrium constant (K_1) and extent of electronic polarizability (α) for $M(\text{acac})_n - I_2$ complexes are listed in Table 1. The interaction of $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ with iodine was also investigated but due to the low solubility of these chelates in carbon tetrachloride and limited accuracy (± 0.0002) of the refractometer, it was not possible to get appropriate variation in the scale. It was, therefore, not possible to calculate equilibrium data (K_1 and α) for these systems. From Table 1, it is clear that the increase in the strength of molecular complexation is in the order of $\text{Be}(\text{acac})_2 < \text{Al}(\text{acac})_3 < \text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3 < \text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3 < \text{VO}(\text{acac})_2 < \text{Co}(\text{acac})_3$. The equilibrium constant data obtained by refractometric methods are comparable with those of spectrophotometric¹ and conductometric² values. Further, it is apparent that data obtained from

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT (K_1), EXTENT OF ELECTRONIC POLARIZATION (α) DATA FOR 1:1 MOLECULAR COMPLEXES OF SOME METAL ACETYLACETONATES WITH IODINE IN CARBON TETRACHLORIDE.

Complex	Equilibrium constant* (K_1), 1. mole ⁻¹					Extent of electronic polarization* (α), $\alpha \times 10^4$		
	Spectro-photometric method ¹	Conductometric method ²	Refractometric method			From Eq. (1)	From Eq. (2)	From Eq. (3)
			From Eq. (1)	From Eq. (2)	From Eq. (3)			
Be(acac) ₂ -I ₂	12.30	17.80	41.66	37.03	20.00	11.76	12.31	12.41
Al(acac) ₃ -I ₂	171.20	169.00	384.61	238.09	172.41	0.74	0.64	0.75
Fe(acac) ₃ -I ₂	—	—	454.54	344.82	256.41	0.75	0.83	1.04
Cr(acac) ₃ -I ₂	—	888.80	909.09	800.00	833.33	0.91	0.89	1.63
VO(acac) ₂ -I ₂	—	—	952.38	909.09	952.38	1.740	1.51	2.31
Co(acac) ₃ -I ₂	—	1666.00	1052.63	952.38	1176.47	1.141	1.70	2.76

* A standard deviation of about $\pm 10-15\%$ in these values has been estimated.

equation (3) are quite comparable with the spectrophotometric values (Table 1) than equations (1 and 2). Thus in order to get best values, one should use the equation (3) instead of equations (1 and 2). Equations (1 and 2) can be used to get qualitative values of equilibrium constants of molecular complexes. The extent of electronic polarizabilities (α) have been found increasing with the increase of equilibrium constants (K_1) except for Be(acac)₂-I₂ complex. Because of the limited accuracy of the instrument (± 0.0002), it was necessary to raise the concentration of solute ($10^{-2}M$) in order to get appropriate variation in the

scale. At this large concentration, the values of K_1 and α are less reliable due to the self association of the solute.

The stoichiometry of the above mentioned molecular complexes has been determined using refractometric titration technique. Through this technique, the change in the refractometric permittivity ($\Delta\phi$) of a solution of one component (acceptor) on addition of successive amount of the other component (donor), has been measured. Now considering the addition of a dipolar donor to a non-dipolar acceptor producing a complex with a refractive index larger than the refractive index of the donor. The addition of a small amount of donor generates an equal amount of complex. The permittivity increase on successive additions of the donor and continues to increase until the equivalent quantities of the donor and acceptor are present. This situation is schematically shown by line XY of Fig. 4 which indicates 1:1 stoichiometry of these complexes.

The formation of above molecular complexes thus provides further support on the pseudo-aromatic character of metal acetylacetonate chelate rings.

Acknowledgement

One of us (R. V.) is thankful to CSIR, New Delhi for the award of Junior Research Fellowship. The authors are grateful to Professor P. C. Nigam (I.I.T., Kanpur) for providing facilities of refractometric measurements.

Fig. 4. Refractometric titration curve for the molecular complexes of metal acetylacetonates with iodine showing 1:1 stoichiometry.

References

1. P. R. SINGH and R. SAHAI, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1970, 23, 269.
2. V. N. BADONI, "Studies on the molecular complexes in metal acetylacetonates", Ph.D. Thesis, (Kanpur University, Kanpur), 1977.
3. R. SAHAI and V. N. BADONI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16A, 1060.
4. A. ARCH and R. C. YOUNG, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1946, 2, 17.
5. R. E. ROWE and M. M. JONES, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1957, 5, 114.
6. R. C. YOUNG, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1946, 2, 25.
7. B. E. BRYANT and W. C. FERNELIUS, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1957, 5, 188.
8. N. V. SIDGWICK, *Chemical elements and their compounds.* (Oxford University Press, London), 1950.
9. R. COOPERATEIN, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1946, 5, 130.
10. R. SAHAI, P. C. PANDE and V. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, 18A, 217.
11. R. SAHAI and V. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, in press.
12. R. SAHAI, V. SINGH and REKHA VERMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, in press.